

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable

Deliverable: D9.5 NEANIAS business perspective assessment report, a report on the NEANIAS business plan and the financial aspects of assessment

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Disclaimer

NEANIAS is a Research and Innovation Action funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, via grant agreement No. 863448.

NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the 'Prototyping New Innovative Services' challenge set out in the 'Roadmap for EOSC' foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community's research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighboring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

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Abstract

The objective of this deliverable is to assess the sustainability of NEANIAS thematic services that are free of charge that is services without revenues. Towards this direction, a technoeconomic model was developed and used.

The first step in this endeavour is to identify the cost elements for the specific services. Several elements have been identified such as cloud resources, tech support personnel, access to dependent core services etc. The conclusions from meetings carried out with the service providers are presented and discussed. The input form distributed to service providers is described.

The derived results using the technoeconomic model are discussed. Existing and future funding per service along with the annual expenses are provided. Cash flows and financial indices like the Net Present Value are estimated in order to assess the investment per service as well as the required funding to ensure services' sustainability.

The business perspectives of both NEANIAS internal and external cases are investigated and discussed. A description of each case is provided while cases business models are also presented.

This deliverable can be used both by NEANIAS partners and other stakeholders involved in EOSC ecosystem since it provides useful figures and guidelines towards NEANIAS services exploitation and sustainability.

1. Introduction

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) federates existing and new data infrastructures with the goal of providing a virtual environment across Europe for researchers to share and reuse data across disciplines and borders. EOSC's mission is to establish the EU as a global leader in research data management unlocking the full potential of data-driven science to European scientists. The main users of EOSC, at least in the first stages of its operation, are European Researchers (~2 million). However, in the next stages, it is expected that EOSC will gradually expand its user base by including both the public and private sectors. As mentioned in the Iron Lady draft [1]:

“The main focus and value of EOSC is to connect such disciplinary infrastructures and research data to enhance disciplinary, cross-disciplinary and transnational research, leading to new scientific discoveries and new insights for society”.

It is thus evident that in order to be a success, EOSC must be widely adopted by researchers, mainly by providing interoperable services that support all aspects of the research lifecycle and enable them to conduct their studies more efficiently and effectively.

NEANIAS promotes Open Science practices and plays active role in the materialization of the EOSC ecosystem by efficiently engaging large scientific and professional communities; actively contributing to the technological, procedural, strategic and business development of EOSC. NEANIAS drives the co-design and delivery of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: Underwater research, Atmospheric research and Space research, each engaging multitudinous academic and business groups, numerous researchers, professionals and governmental entities.

Although the services provided mainly by academic partners will be free of charge, based on their business model, they are accompanied by significant costs related to the development, maintenance and operation. Thus, self-sustainability seems to be impossible leading to the need of funding mechanisms and resources ensuring the sustainability of the provided services. However, in order to estimate the required funds, it is important to derive the costs related to the provided services.

The first step in the process was to conduct a thorough analysis of existing documentation and conduct a series of interviews with service providers from NEANIAS consortium in order to gather information on two key aspects: the nature of the services and components, as well as their dimensioning rules. Service providers were also asked for changes of the initial business models provided in Deliverable D9.3.

After examining the existing documentation, the main services were assessed. Cost components have been divided into their various cost categories, which include all forms of fixed and variable costs that may be required in order to deliver all of the services. Compute resources, data storage expenses, bandwidth costs, human resources, equipment, and tech support costs are just a few examples.

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Service providers have been contacted and requested to respond to a series of cost-related inquiries. Iteratively, in-depth interviews with the service providers were conducted to have a deeper understanding of all the cost-related issues. These costs have been gathered and analyzed, and they will be included in NEANIAS services' cost model. The expenses collected in the previous phase were sorted and modelled in a spreadsheet, allowing an estimate of the total costs of running NEANIAS services.

A study of the European funding schemes has been performed, identifying key schemes available in Europe, at both national and transnational levels, that would meet the needs of NEANIAS services.

Finally, both internal and external NEANIAS cases were investigated. The cases were described while their business perspectives were discussed.

2. Services Included in the Study

This first study considered all NEANIAS services (listed below) following a “free model” (free of charge – no revenues). A brief description of each service along with its business model canvas (with changes – if any) were provided in order to have a complete picture of the business potential per service. More details about the business model of each service can be found in Deliverable D9.3.

2.1. ATMO-SEISM Service

The ATMO-Seism service, developed by the Università Degli Studi di Milano Bicocca and the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, aims to correlate gas emissions with earthquake parameters and atmospheric conditions in order to better understand the interaction between tectonic activity, volcanism, and gas release through faults, fractures, and volcanic craters (e.g. radon, CO₂, SO₂ etc.).

Figure 1 : ATMO-SEISM business model canvas

2.2. Astra Data Navigator Service (ADN)

ADN (Astra Data Navigator) is a Virtual Reality tool developed by Aerospace Logistic Technology Engineering Company (ALTEC). It was created to allow for the representation of

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massive datasets from star catalogues in 3D environments, as well as a realistic time simulation for many other celestial entities. These capabilities have been enhanced through the analysis of visualized and simulated data.

Figure 2: ADN business model canvas

2.3. ViaLactea Service

The ViaLactea Service aims to investigate the Milky Way's star formation process by utilizing astrophysical surveys of the Galactic Plane. The ViaLactea Visual Analytic (VLVA) tool combines several methods of visualization to accomplish the analysis, such as 2D intensity images with 3D molecular spectral cubes, to explore the association between diverse data. The ViaLactea Knowledge Base manages all of the underlying data (VLKB). The VLKB contains 2D and 3D surveys (velocity cubes), numerical model outputs, point-like and diffuse object catalogues, and allows retrieval of all accessible datasets as well as cut-outs on the positional and/or velocity axes. Additionally, a Montage Map Merging service allows adjacent datasets to be merged. INAF-Istituto Nazionale di Astrofisica provides the ViaLactea Service.

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Figure 3: ViaLactea business model canvas

2.4. Compact and Extended Sources Automated Recognition Service (CAESAR Service)

CAESAR Service, developed by INAF, is a simple way to segment astrophysical FITS maps, allowing for the extraction and characterisation of both compact (e.g. stars, galaxies) and extended (e.g. galactic filaments, supernovae remnants) sources.

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Figure 4: CAESAR business model canvas

3. Methodology and Spreadsheet Structure

3.1. Methodology

In this section, the methodology that will be used in order to assess the sustainability of NEANIAS services is described.

3.1.1. Elements of the technoeconomic model

Several methodologies and cost models have been identified and described in Deliverable D9.2 that could be potential used in order to estimate the costs per services and assess their sustainability. Towards this direction service Providers were contacted. Multiple interactions were carried out. Initially, a virtual meeting with all the service providers were performed in order to present them the defined cost elements and defined cost models. From the interactions, it has been concluded that all service providers were not able to provide information in the level of details requested by the defined cost models. Thus, a simplified methodology was decided and developed. This methodology is based on well-known techniques [2]-[3] and mathematical models that were extensively used in several technoeconomic studies in ICT [5]-[9].

An overall description of the required tasks and how these are interconnected is illustrated in Figure 5. The overall objective is to forecast all expenses and funding/revenues associated with the selected services for a particular time period (study period). The blue color represents initial inputs regarding the selected service while the yellow represents calculations based on the previous assumptions. The green color shows the results. The main elements of Figure 5 are described below:

- Usage requirements: expected usage of the service by the users
- Service “architecture”: description of the service and identification of all the elements that are necessary for its operation
- Number of users: this as an estimation of the expected number of users of the service
- Service tariffs: the amount of money that the users have to pay in order to access/use the service. It should be highlighted that for the services to be investigated service tariff is set to zero since they are following the free model.
- Funding/Revenues: Existing or expected funding as well as an estimation of Revenues based on the number of subscribers and the service tariffs. In the study under investigation revenues are zero.
- Resources price: the price of the required resources and their evolution over time
- Maintenance/upgrade: the cost of maintaining/upgrading the service
- Investments: the cost of resources related to the service
- Other: includes parameters used for the calculations such as study period, discount rate, tax rate etc.

Figure 5: Technoeconomic methodology used for the assessment of NEANIAS services sustainability

3.1.2. DCF Analysis

Discounted Cash Flow (DCF) analysis takes into account the time value of money and the risks of investing in a project. Towards this end, cash flows for future investments are estimated and discounted in order to calculate the Present Value (PV). The main advantages of DCF analysis are that it is a simple quantitative method to implement, is widely accepted and provides clear and consistent metrics (e.g., NPV, IRR) for all kinds of projects.

3.1.3. Key outputs of the model

In the evaluation of investment scenarios, there can be several points of view. Depending on the complexity of the scenario, various commonly used indicators (like NPV) can give differing results in comparisons.

Because of this, it is often necessary to use several figures of merit for the studies to “get” a thorough understanding of the economic issues related to each scenario.

3.1.3.1. Investments

The first output is the investment cost of the project. The investments are usually spread over the study period. To “get” a single figure of merit for the total investment, the future investments are discounted to the start of the study period by using the conventional discounting formula.

3.1.3.2. Cash balance

The Cash Balance (Cumulative Cash Flow) time-series is a very informative figure for a service scenario. A typical Cash balance curve for a network scenario goes first deeply down to the negative side because of the high initial investments. If the scenario is profitable, the cash flow turns positive fairly soon and the Cash Balance curve starts to rise. The lowest point in the

Cash Balance curve gives the amount of funding required for the project. The point in time when the Cash Balance turns positive gives the Payback Period for the project.

If the scenario under investigation is more complex, it is still possible to use the Cash Balance curve as an indicator for the profitability of the scenario. In this case, it is important to study the trend of cash flow at the end of the study period.

3.1.3.3. Net present value (NPV)

The Net Present Value gives a single figure of merit for a project. Its definition is the Sum of Discounted Cash Flows plus the Discounted Rest Value of the project. It gives the monetary value of the whole project in today's money. It is a good indicator for the profitability of the scenario, especially in these cases where the Payback Period cannot be used because major investments are spread out in time.

The weakest point in this figure of merit is the definition or calculation of the rest value of the network. There are several ways to define this value. The usual approach uses the bookkeeping value of the network as the Rest Value because it is the only figure that can be calculated from the inputs already available.

3.2. Spreadsheet/Input Form Structure

In this section, the spreadsheet sent to service providers in order collect their inputs is presented. After the development of the technoeconomic model and the definition of the cost elements, an email was sent asking service providers to fill in and return a spreadsheet/input form.

In general, the provided input from this first phase were of low quality. It was followed by a series of phone calls and email exchanges, explaining them the requested forms, which increased the quality of the provided input to some extent. The main factors of the limited input provided by service providers are as follows:

- Service providers are not aware of the expected users of their services (the market).
- Most of them were not aware of the required resources and how these are scaling up since most of the services have not yet had a high number of users.
- The provided dimensioning rules and costs were usually estimates and variable (under-estimating and over-estimating the provided service costs).
- There is no information about the price of competitive services.
- It is thus evident that to really comprehend both the dimensioning rules and the costs of NEANIAS services, more time and effort will be required.

Given the difficulties of service providers to collect such information, the spreadsheet was simplified and improved through an interactive and iterative approach. The simplified layout reflects the lack of the available detailed costing information. The structure of the simplified tables are as follows:

- 1st Sheet
 - Period: how the required information is reported to us (e.g. annually)
 - Price: the price that the users will pay for the provided service
 - Price of other products: Price of competitive products

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- Market
 - Market size: The number of potential users
 - Penetration: Percentage of the market that will become users of the service
 - Number of users: Users of the service
- Usage of average user: Proportion of time an average user is accessing the service
- Load per unit
 - CPU (vcore): How many vcore are required to deliver the service to one user
 - Storage (GB): How many GBytes of RAM are needed to deliver the service to one user
 - Networking (GB): The required capacity for the exchange of file/info for this user
 - Tech support: How many persons are needed to support the smooth delivery of the service
- Cost
 - CPU: The cost of 1 vcore
 - Storage: The cost for 1GB
 - Networking: The cost for 1GB
 - Tech support: The cost for 1 support person
- 2nd Sheet (Funding)
 - Amount of current and future Funding Sources
 - Membership
 - National
 - EC Projects
 - International
- 3rd Sheet (implementation expenses)
 - Period from: Starting period of implementation
 - Period to: Ending period of implementation
 - Type: The type of implementation (e.g. investment)
 - Description: Description of implementation (e.g. platform 1 implementation)
 - Total costs: The cost of the described implementation
- 4th Sheet (Other (proportional) expenses)
 - Name: Name/Type of expense (e.g. management/overheads)
 - Calculated on: The cost category on which it is calculated (e.g. revenue)
 - Percentage: Percentage of the cost of the selected cost category

In the first sheet, service providers are invited to provide as much periods as possible in order to estimate the evolution of the users and that of the required resources. In the fourth sheet, service providers are asked to fill in any expense that is related to the operation and delivery of the service.

4. Study data – Assumptions

In this section, the data and the basic assumptions of the techno-economic model are presented.

4.1. Study period

In most of the cases, a study period of at least seven (-7-) years is used for the estimations, regarding the profitability of the cases involving telecommunications players.

In this case a study period of eight (-8-) years is used, starting from 2019 and ending in 2026.

Table 1: Study Period

Parameter	Value
Duration	10
Start Year	2019
End Year	2026

The first four years are usually used for the development of the service. In addition, the running period starts at the fourth year when the first users are accessing the service.

4.2. Financial assumptions

The objective is to estimate all the necessary costs to develop and run a service as well as the required funds ensuring its sustainability.

The network is expected to generate revenue through the lifetime of the product. Deducted from the revenue stream are depreciation, operating cost, general administration cost and taxes.

To judge the model, several cash flows are calculated. To calculate discounted cash flows, a discount rate of 5-10% is used in most of the cases. A tax rate is also used in order to estimate the taxes in case of profits.

Table 2: Financial assumptions

Parameter	Value
Discount Factor	8%
Income taxes (if applicable)	20%

4.2.1. Dimensioning of the required core services

In order to estimate the required number of “licenses” for the required/dependent core services, dimensioning rules and prices are defined and shown in Table 3.

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Table 3: Required core services

Service	Dimensioning Rule	Indicative Price (€)
AAI	1 / 2000 users	100
Accounting	1 / 200 users	200
Logging	1 / 500 users	200
Compute orchestrator	1 / 200 users	500

5. Financial Results

In this section, the results of the developed techno-economic model are presented and analysed per service. The results include a detailed analysis of the expenses and the financial outcome as expressed by the financial indices discussed before.

5.1. Financial analysis of ATMO-SEISM service

5.1.1. Demand Analysis

The first step for the technoeconomic and sustainability analysis is to define the potential number of users. Towards this direction, the service provider was asked to provide an estimation of the expected number of users per year. Desk research was also carried out to define the number of researchers for the specific area. Using the collected information and data, a forecast of service's users in the study period was derived (Figure 6).

Figure 6: ATMO-SEISM number of users

From Figure 6, one can see that there are no users in the first years of implementation/development. The first users are observed in the fourth year while the number of users slightly increases throughout the study period.

5.1.2. Expenses Analysis

At the beginning of the eight-year study period, ATMO-SEISM service provider invested in the implementation/development of the service. In the following years, the provider will invest in the cloud resources, the required access to core service and the support personnel in order to run the service.

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Figure 7 illustrates the required annual expenses of ATMO-SEISM service provider. As shown the figure, expenses are increasing with time due to the increase of service’s users. It should be noted that other expenses include overheads (e.g. management costs).

Figure 7: ATMO-SEISM service provider’s expenses (in k€)

To have a better insight of the expenditures, expenses breakdown for the entire study period is shown in Figure 8. As illustrated, tech support personnel is the main contributing factor followed by implementation costs.

Figure 8: ATMO-SEISM total expenses breakdown

5.1.3. Financial Indices

All individual cash flows as well as a cumulative cash flow line are presented in Figure 9 for the ATMO-SEISM service. The cumulative discounted cash flow, widely known as the cash balance, summarizes the total profit/loss at the end of each year of the business case.

In this case, we assumed that the service provider has also to pay for the required cloud resources. The first observation from Figure 9 is that the balance is negative in the whole running period. However, this is expected since ATMO-SEISM service is following a free business model and thus there are no revenues to cover the expenses. Our calculations show that the NPV for this “investment” is approximately -€236 thousand. It is thus evident that ATMO-SEISM service is not self-sustainable. Indeed, in order to ensure the sustainability of ATMO-SEISM service, about €385 thousand funding is required for the whole period. From Figure 9, it is straightforward to find the required funding per year. In chapter 6, potential European funding mechanisms that could support the sustainability of the services are presented.

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Figure 9: ATMO-SEISM cash flows by year

As mentioned above, Figure 9 presents the case where the service provider has to pay for the required infrastructure. However, it is possible EU to support the existing situation where the required infrastructure is provided for free to the service provider (e.g. EGI, GARR, GEANT etc.).

This case is presented in Figure 10. Our calculations show that the NPV for this “investment” is approximately -€218 thousand. It is evident that although the results are somehow improved, the service is still unsustainable requiring a funding of a about €355 thousand for the whole period. This is somehow expected since the bigger part of expenses is attributed to tech support personnel.

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Figure 10: ATMO-SEISM cash flows by year excluding cloud resources cost

5.2. Financial analysis of ViaLactea service

5.2.1. Demand Analysis

Following the same approach as in the ATMO-SEISM case, the expected users throughout the study period were derived (Figure 11).

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Figure 11: ViaLactea number of users

As shown in Figure 11, there were some “users” during the implementation/development phase (2019 – 2021) for evaluation and validation purposes (in orange). It should be highlighted that these users are not affecting the financial results since the infrastructure was provided by GARR and the support by the development team. The first “real” users appear in 2022. It should also be noted that the number of users will increase reaching 100 users at the end of the study period.

5.2.2. Expenses Analysis

In Figure 12, the annual expenses of ViaLactea service provider are depicted. The implementation/development will be carried out in the first four years. From the fourth year when the first users are expected, several costs related to cloud resources, the dependent core services, support etc will be added. Other expenses include overheads (e.g. management costs). It should also be highlighted that for the expected number of users, the required resources do not depend on the users apart from storage which slightly increases in the third year of operation. On the other hand, the required tech support personnel is increasing with the number of users.

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Figure 12: ViaLactea service provider's expenses (in k€)

To have a better insight of the expenditures, expenses breakdown for the entire study period is shown in Figure 13. As illustrated, cloud resources is the main contributing factor followed by implementation and tech support personnel costs.

Figure 13: ViaLactea total expenses breakdown

5.2.3. Financial Indices

All individual cash flows as well as a cumulative cash flow line are presented in Figure 14 for the ViaLactea service. In this case, we assumed that the service provider has also to pay for the required cloud resources. As depicted in Figure 13, the balance is negative in the whole running period. However, this is expected since ViaLactea service is following a free business model and thus there are no revenues to cover the expenses. Our calculations show that the NPV for this “investment” is approximately -€310 thousand. It is thus evident that ViaLactea service is not self-sustainable. Indeed, in order to ensure the sustainability of the service, about €500 thousand funding is required for the whole period. From Figure 13, one can easily derive the required funding per year.

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Figure 14: ViaLactea cash flows by year

On the other hand, in the case that EU or countries will support the existing situation where the required infrastructure is provided for free to the service providers (e.g. EGI, GARR, GEANT etc.), the NPV is approximately -€115 thousand. It is evident that although the results are somehow improved, the service is still unsustainable requiring a funding of a about €185 thousand for the whole period. This is somehow expected since the bigger part of expenses is attributed to cloud resources.

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Figure 15: ViaLactea cash flows by year excluding cloud resources cost

However, it should be stressed that ViaLactea service provider has already secured €280 thousand from another EU project till 2026 while €150 thousand funding is expected next year from national and internal funding. Thus, ViaLactea service can be assumed sustainable in the following years for both cases (with and without the need to pay the required infrastructure).

5.3. Financial analysis of CEASAR service

5.3.1. Demand Analysis

By combined the input from the service provider with the statistical data about the number of researchers in the sector, one can forecast the expected number of CEASAR service users in the following years (Figure 16).

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Figure 16: CEASAR number of users

As can be seen in Figure 16, there were 15 and 25 evaluation and validation users in 2020 and 2021 respectively. For the same reasons with the ViaLactea case, these users are not affecting the financial analysis. In 2022, we had the first 50 “real” users. It should also be noted that the number of users at the end of the study period will be 200.

5.3.2. Expenses Analysis

Figure 17 illustrates the annual expenses of CEASAR service provider. The implementation/development will be carried out in the first four years. The last five years of the study period, the service provider will have several costs related to cloud resources, the dependent core services, support etc. Other expenses include overheads (e.g. management costs). It should also be highlighted that for the expected number of users, the required resources do not change with users. On the other hand, the required tech support personnel is increasing with the number of users.

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Figure 17: CEASAR service provider’s expenses (in k€)

To have a better insight of the expenditures, expenses breakdown for the entire study period is shown in Figure 18. As shown, cloud resources can be accounted for 46% of the total expenses being the leading cost category.

Figure 18: CEASAR total expenses breakdown

5.3.3. Financial Indices

Cash flows and cash balance are illustrated in Figure 19 for the CEASAR service. The case where the required infrastructure is not provided for free to the service provider will be investigated. As shown in Figure 19, the balance is negative in the whole running period. However, this is expected since CEASAR service is following a free business model and thus there are no revenues to cover the expenses. Our calculations show that the NPV for this “investment” is approximately -€270 thousand. It is thus evident that CEASAR service is not self-sustainable. Indeed, in order to ensure the sustainability of the service, about €430 thousand funding is required for the whole period. The required funding per year can be derived from Figure 19.

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Figure 19: CEASAR cash flows by year

On the other hand, in the case that EU or countries will fund the infrastructure by providing for free to the service provider (e.g. EGI, GARR, GEANT etc.), the NPV is approximately -€77 thousand. It is evident that although the results are somehow improved, the service is still unsustainable requiring a funding of a about €125 thousand for the whole period. This is somehow expected since half of the expenses is coming from the cost of cloud resources.

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Figure 20: CEASAR cash flows by year excluding cloud resources cost

However, the service provider has already received funding (national and internal) of about €170 thousand which can compensate some of the running costs of the service for the next two years. In addition, CEASAR service provider is expecting national and internal funding of about €150 thousand funding helping the sustainability of the service.

5.4. Financial analysis of ADN service

ADN service has the simplest business model. ADN service is a free client tool. Thus, it does not require maintenance or infrastructure in order to run. The only costs related to ADN service are research and development costs (development and renew/upgrade of the service).

5.4.1. Demand Analysis

The expected number of ADN service users in the following years are shown in Figure 21.

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Figure 21: ADN number of users

As in the previous cases, the first users are expected in 2022. However, contrary to the other services, the expected users are expected to grow faster reaching 1600 users at the end of the study period.

5.4.2. Expenses Analysis

Figure 22 illustrates the annual expenses of ADN service provider. As mention before, due to the selected business model, the provider do not have other expenses than those related to the development/implementation and renew/upgrade of the service. The implementation/development will be carried out in the first four years. The second half of the study period, the service provider will renew/upgrade the service.

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Figure 22: ADN service provider's expenses (in k€)

To have a better insight of the expenditures, expenses breakdown for the entire study period is shown in Figure 23. As shown, the total expenses are almost equally distributed between the two expenses with renew/upgrade being slightly higher. This can be attributed to the fact that in the last year of the study period a second upgrade of the service is scheduled.

Figure 23: CEASAR total expenses breakdown

5.4.3. Financial Indices

Cash flows and cash balance are illustrated in Figure 24 for the ADN service. As shown, the funding covers all the implementation costs. Thus, the service provider should find funding to cover the renew/upgrade of the service in the following years. Our calculations show that the NPV for this “investment” is approximately -€60 thousand. It is thus evident that ADN service is not self-sustainable. Hence, in order to ensure the sustainability of the service, about €100 thousand funding is required for the whole period. The required funding per year can also be derived from Figure 24.

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Figure 24: ADN cash flows by year

However, the service provider declared that more than the required funding is expected in the following years from EU sources able to cover the expenses of service upgrade.

6. Funding mechanisms that could support the sustainability of services

Since this first set of services are mainly provided by academic partners, it is not expected to have revenues as per the business models described earlier. Thus, in order to cover the expenses for the operation, maintenance and upgrade of the services ensuring their sustainability, several funding mechanisms should be investigated.

This document analyses funding tools available to the public and private sector at the European level. The European level funds involves organisations (such as the European Space Agency) that are managed by a set of countries that can be different to the EU Member States.

When the information is available, each fund is assigned the following evaluations:

Relevance: an evaluation is provided (high, medium or low) on how the fund addresses EoSC and EoSC related services and issues

Addressees: is the organisation which attributes the fund

Beneficiary: physical or moral person that can request the fund

Amounts available: total amounts attributed to the fund

Investment covered: which kind of investment beneficiaries can expect to cover

Type of support: definition of the type of funding tool proposed by the programme

Percentage of funding coverage: what percentage will the fund cover as a total of the investment

Links: some of the major links related to the analysis are provided in addition to the footnotes.

6.1. European Union funds

In 2020, the European Union had to approve its budget for the period 2021-2027. At the same time, the major economic crisis generated by the Covid-19 pandemic in its Member States required extraordinary funding by the EU to sustain their economies, which translated into the adoption of the Recovery Plan for Europe. The Recovery Plan for Europe comprises the EU's long-term budget 2021-2027, called the multiannual financial framework, which was approved on December 17 and is in place since 1 January 2021, coupled with the NextGenerationEU initiative, which is a temporary instrument designed to boost the recovery.

The greatest -and most argued- novelty of the Recovery Plan for Europe is the NextGenerationEU, a €750 billion temporary recovery instrument that will allow the Commission to raise funds on the capital market. This instrument was approved by the European Council on December 10, 2020 and will need to be ratified by the European Parliament and the Parliaments of the Member States.

The Recovery plan for Europe will offer a total of €1,8 trillion to help rebuild a post-Covid-19 Europe. Within this stimulus package, €143,4 billion are earmarked for the single market, innovation and digital questions.

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It should be noted that to attribute the funds of the Recovery Plan, the Commission is mainly supplementing a number of its existing programmes for the 2021-2027 period, such as Horizon Europe or the InvestEU Programm which were bolstered up.

6.1.1. The InvestEU programme 2021-2027

This programme is important because it brings together under one roof the multitude of EU financial instruments currently available such as the European Fund for Strategic Investments (EFSI) provided by the European Investment Bank (EIB) and analysed under that section, the Connecting European Facility (CEF) and financing tools used by the Horizon Europe programme such as the Innovfin Equity and the EIB such as the InnovFin SME guarantee. The programme expands the successful model of the Investment Plan for Europe, the Juncker Plan. With InvestEU, the Commission will trigger at least €650 billion in additional investment. The InvestEU programme's novelty is that it will allegedly provide a simplified and streamlined investment support with just one set of rules and procedures for all its EU financial instruments. The **InvestEU Fund**, which is part of the InvestEU programme, will mobilize public and private investment using guarantees from the EU budget, is part of this programme.

The InvestEU fund is composed of:

- the EU long-term budget which has attributed €15.2 billion to the InvestEU fund;
- an estimated € 47,5 billion guaranteed from the EU budget and financial partners' resources which comprises **€ 11,25 billion for research and innovation and the same amount for SMEs**; and
- as for the Juncker plan, the programme will crowd-in public and private investors which should multiply these instruments to reach a total estimated investment of at least € 650 billion.

6.1.2. Horizon Europe

Relevance: High

Addressees: European Commission

Beneficiaries: Public and private sector, NGO, academia

Amounts available: €97,6 billion, €3,5 billion of which will be allocated under the InvestEU Fund

Investment covered: depending on programme

Type of support: loans, guarantees, equity and other market-based instruments

Percentage of funding coverage: depending on programme

Links: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_18_4041

Horizon Europe is the new 2021-2027 research program which has a budget allocation of €97,6 billion, €3,5 billion of which will be allocated under the InvestEU Fund. The innovation window of InvestEU will allow using loans, guarantees, equity and other market-based instruments to mobilise public and private investment in research and innovation.

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The Global Challenges and Industrial Competitiveness pillar (€52,7 billion) directly supports research relating to societal challenges, reinforces technological and industrial capacities, and sets EU-wide missions to tackle problems. It also includes activities pursued by the Joint Research Centre (€2,2 billion) which supports EU and national policymakers with independent scientific evidence and technical support.

The Open Innovation pillar (€13,5 billion) focuses on market-creating innovation via the European Innovation Council (€10 billion). It will help develop the overall European innovation landscape, including by strengthening the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT) to foster the integration of business, research, higher education and entrepreneurship (€3 billion)¹.

The European Parliament and the Council of the EU reached in March and April 2019 a provisional agreement on Horizon Europe. The European Parliament endorsed the provisional agreement on 17 April 2019. The EU institutions reached a political agreement on Horizon Europe on 11 December 2020. The agreement is subject to formal approval by the European Parliament and the Council of the EU. The first Horizon Europe Strategic Plan (2021-2024) was published at the beginning of 2021.

Horizon Europe: Preliminary structure

Figure 25: Horizon Europe Based on the Commission Proposal for Horizon Europe, the common understanding between co-legislators and the Partial General Approach, both approved in April 2019 (Source: EC)

¹ Extract from EU funding for Research and Innovation 2021-2027, European Commission, 7 June 2018

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The *Orientations towards the first Strategic Plan for Horizon Europe* are ambitious, forward looking and address planetary problems together with far-reaching advanced scientific, technological and societal challenges. It should be noted that the EU Commission wishes to develop new approaches and instruments for maximizing the impact of its actions. The instruments that it wishes to tackle are **missions** to achieve a measurable goal within a set timeframe with impact for science and technology and/or society and citizens that could not have been achieved through individual actions. In addition, the EU Commission intends to develop **European Partnership** initiatives where the EU together with private and/or public partners commit to jointly support the development and implementation of a programme of research and innovation activities. The partners could represent industry, universities, research organisations, bodies with a public service remit at local, regional, national or international level or civil society organisations including foundations and NGOs.

The complexity of having several projects with a wide range of consortium partners is suffocating, and it is the primary reason why there is a clear lack of harmonisation, if not outright communication, between different actors in the EOSC ecosystem. As a result, continuing in this direction may be destructive in the long run, despite the fact that it is clearly beneficial, from the financial point of view, to the various participants in the short term.

6.2. Regional Funds

The EU's Regional Policy targets all regions and cities in the European Union in order to support job creation, business competitiveness, economic growth, sustainable development, and improve citizens' quality of life.

Regional Policy is delivered through two main funds: the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and the Cohesion Fund (CF). Together with the European Social Fund (ESF), the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF), they make up the European Structural and Investment (ESI) Funds.

6.2.1. European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and Cohesion Fund (CF)

Relevance: Low-Medium

Addressees: Regions

Beneficiaries: public bodies, some private sector organisations (especially small businesses), universities, associations, NGOs and voluntary organisations.

Amounts available: €242,9 billion for EU regional funding (2021- 2027)

Investment covered: depends on programme

Type of support: it will depend on the program defined within each country. Support can take the form of grants, financial instruments or prizes or a combination thereof

Percentage of funding coverage: varies according to programme

Links:

https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/it/document.html?reference=EPRS_BRI%282018%29625141

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<https://cohesiondata.ec.europa.eu/countries/LU#>

The purpose of the ERDF is to strengthen economic and social cohesion in the European Union by correcting imbalances between its regions by investing in the infrastructure and services of underdeveloped regions. One of its priority areas is **innovation and research**.

The funds are managed by the Member States (MS). A partnership agreement is made between the European Commission and each MS, leading to a series of investment programmes channelling the funding to the different regions and projects in accordance with the policy areas defined by the European Union in each budgetary cycle.

The European Regional Development Fund and Cohesion Fund 2021-2027 will be regulated by a **new single regulation covering the ERDF and Cohesion Fund funds**, in accordance with a proposal of the Commission currently under review by the EU Parliament². In January 2021, the European Institutions have entered into the *Trilogue* negotiations i.e. tripartite meetings between Parliament, the Council and the Commission to approve the regulation.

The current proposal identifies the specific objectives and scope of support for both funds, including non-eligible activities, such as broadband infrastructure in areas with already good coverage. The majority of ERDF funding (a minimum of 85 % for countries that have a Gross National Income higher than the EU average) will focus on **smart growth** and the **green economy**, while the fund will also support other activities such as connectivity, social issues and local development. The main focus of ERDF are research and innovation, ICT, SMEs and low carbon economy. ERDF will support: a) investments in infrastructure; b) investments in access to services; c) productive investments in SMEs; d) equipment, software and intangible assets; e) information, communication, studies, networking, cooperation, exchange of experience and activities involving clusters; and f) technical assistance³. In the new budgetary cycle, the Cohesion Fund will continue to focus predominantly on environmental and transport infrastructure.

The following objectives are pursued in relation to smart growth and green economy, the two proposed priorities in the new period⁴

² Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down common provisions on the European Regional Development Fund, the European Social Fund Plus, the Cohesion Fund, and the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund and financial rules for those and for the Asylum and Migration Fund, the Internal Security Fund and the Border Management and Visa Instrument, Strasbourg, 29.5.2018 COM(2018) 375 final 2018/0196 (COD)

³ Briefing, EU Legislation in Progress 2021-2027 MFF, European Regional Development Fund and Cohesion Fund 2021-2027, January 2020

⁴ Commission Staff Working Document Impact Assessment, Accompanying the document Proposals for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the European Regional Development Fund and on the Cohesion Fund, Strasbourg, 29.5.2018 SWD(2018) 282 final

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Table 4: Objectives related to smart growth and green economy

Policy Objective	Specific Objective	Common output indicators	Common result indicators
A smarter Europe - innovative and smart industrial transformation	1.1 Enhancing innovation capacity	RCO 01 - Enterprises supported (of which: micro, small, medium, large) RCO 02 - Enterprises supported by grants RCO 03 - Enterprises supported by FIs RCO 04 - Enterprises with non-financial support RCO 05 - Start-ups supported RCO 06 - Researchers working in supported research facilities RCO 07 - Research institutions participating in joint research projects RCO 08 - Nominal value of research and innovation equipment RCO 10 - Enterprises cooperating with research institutions	RCR 01 - Jobs created in supported entities RCR 02 - Private investments matching public support (of which: grants, FIs) RCR 03 - SMEs introducing product or process innovation RCR 04 - SMEs introducing marketing or organisational innovation RCR 05 - SMEs innovating in-house RCR 06 - Patent applications submitted to EPO RCR 07 - Trademark and design applications RCR 08 - Public-private co-publications
	1.2 Reaping the benefits of digitalisation for citizens, companies and governments	RCO 12 - Enterprises supported to digitise their products and services RCO 13 - Digital services and products developed for enterprises RCO 14 - Public institutions supported to develop digital services and applications	RCR 11 - Users of new public digital services and applications RCR 12 - Users of new digital products, services and applications developed by enterprises RCR 13 - Enterprises reaching high digital intensity RCR 14 - Enterprises using public digital services
	1.3 Enhancing growth and competitiveness of SMEs	RCO 15 - Capacity of incubation created	RCR 16 - High growth enterprises supported RCR 17 - 3-year old enterprises surviving in the market RCR 18 - SMEs using incubator services one year after the incubator creation RCR 19 - Enterprises with higher turnover

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	1.4 Developing skills for smart specialisation, industrial transition and entrepreneurship	RCO 16 - Stakeholders participating in entrepreneurial discovery process RCO 17 - Acquisition of know-how for smart specialisation and industrial transition (million euro)	RCR 24 - Staff supported to gain know how for smart specialisation and industrial transition RCR 25 - Value added per employee in supported SMEs
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Type of support:

Member States can provide support in accordance with the regulation which will come into effect⁵ by way of grants which can have the form of: (a) reimbursement of eligible costs actually incurred by a beneficiary or the private partner of PPP operations and paid in implementing operations, including contributions in kind and depreciation; (b) unit costs; (c) lump sums; (d) flat-rate financing; and (e) a combination of the forms.

Members States can also offer in relation to grants: flat-rate financing for indirect costs, direct staff costs and flat-rate financing for eligible costs other than direct staff costs.

It is also interesting to note that the Regulation offers the possibility to Member States to contribute to financial instruments in order to achieve specific objectives. These contributions are required to provide support only for new investments that are financially viable and that do not obtain sufficient funding from market source.

6.3. Institutional projects

6.3.1. ESA (European Space Agency) projects

Relevance: High

Addressees: ESA

Beneficiaries: private and public sector

Amounts available: not available

Investment covered: projects for the satellite communication industry to introduce innovative space-based solutions systems into the commercial market.

Type of support: invitation to tender, call for ideas, call for proposals.

Percentage of funding coverage: depends on partnership

Links:

[https://www.esa.int/Applications/Telecommunications_Integrated_Applications/Partnership Projects](https://www.esa.int/Applications/Telecommunications_Integrated_Applications/Partnership_Projects)

ESA's Partnership Projects provide the satellite communication industry with the environment to introduce innovative space-based solutions systems into the commercial market. ESA has

⁵ *Op.cit.*: same proposal regulation as under note 4, Articles 47 to 52

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implemented several Partnership Projects through its ARTES programme (Advanced Research in Telecommunications Systems).

The objective of these projects is to federate the European industry around large-scale programmes and developing innovative cutting-edge solutions in partnership with private or public operators. Partnership Projects enable greater risk sharing where ESA bears the risks related to the development of innovative solutions and the operators assume the commercial risks in answer to market needs.

EU companies that wish to partner with ESA can respond to an invitation to tender, a call for ideas, or a call for proposals.

In addition, ESA organises the e-ESA investor forum. They screen the portfolio of more than 1500 businesses and select 10 of the most promising ones and match them with the investors and partners to help these companies in their growth.

6.3.2. EUREKA⁶

Eureka is an intergovernmental decentralised organisation for pan-European research and development funding and coordination EUREKA is an open platform of 45-member countries including the EU, for international cooperation in innovation.

In general, organisations participating in international R&D projects are eligible for funding through Eureka's Network projects: Globalstars, Eurostars and Clusters programmes. Obtaining funding by Eureka requires to contact first the responsible Ministry and the responsible National Research authority of the country.

EUREKA 'Clusters' programmes are long-term, strategically significant industrial initiatives. They operate with a large number of participants to develop inclusive technologies of key importance for European competitiveness mainly in ICT, energy and more recently in the biotechnology and automation sectors. Eureka Clusters have had an impact on the ability of the European microelectronics sector to compete with other continents.

The Eureka Clusters are:

- CELTIC NEXT: Telecommunications (see below)
- EURIPIDES: Electronic packaging and smart systems
- ITEA 3: Software-intensive systems
- PENTA: Micro and nanoelectronics enabled systems and applications
- EUROGIA2020: Low-carbon energy technologies
- METALLURGY EUROPE: New metals
- SMART: Advance manufacturing programme

EUREKA also operates through: Umbrellas which are thematic networks within the Eureka framework that focus on a specific technology area or business sector. The main goal of an umbrella is to facilitate the generation of EUREKA projects in its own target area.

⁶ EUREKA being organised in sub-projects such as clusters the summarized information is provided in the cluster: Celtic-Next

6.3.2.1. CELTIC-NEXT projects

Relevance: High

Addressees: National Project Coordinator (NPC)

Beneficiaries: all types of companies, universities and research organisations

Investment covered: between €1M to more than €70 M in total project budget, and include from 2 to over 50 partners.

Type of support: Funding, Partner search, Advice services and support tool

Percentage of funding coverage: up to 50% through public funding, depending on the national funding rules, of

Links: <https://www.celticnext.eu/call-information/>. Registration page is <https://cluster-projects.eurestools.eu>

CELTIC-NEXT is the EUREKA Cluster for next-generation communications enabling the digital society, which orchestrates international collaborative projects in the Information and Communications Technology domain. It is an industry-driven initiative, involving all the major ICT industry players as well as many SMEs, service providers, and research institutions and includes a wide scope of ICT topics based on new high-performance communications networks supporting data-rich applications and advanced services.

The projects are open to any type of company, large industry, small companies, universities and research organisations, even to companies outside the EUREKA countries. The projects are bottom-up, i.e. without the need to follow defined programme objectives. However, they must cover ICT related research items.

They receive public funding, depending on the national funding rules, of up to 50%. The Project consortia need to have at least two different partners from two different EUREKA countries (one must be a EUREKA Member Country and one a EUREKA Member Country or a EUREKA Associated Country).

The projects are typically between €1M and up to more than €70M in total project budget and include from 2 to over 50 partners. Project duration is generally between 24 and 36 months.

6.4. National Research Funds

Relevance: High

Addressees: EU countries

Beneficiaries: all types of companies, universities and research organisations

Amounts available: per program

Investment covered: Depend on the program

Type of support: it will depend on the program defined within each country

Percentage of funding coverage: depends on the program

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Links: [https://www.scienceeurope.org/about-us/members/?type=Research%20Funding%20Organisation%20\(RFO\)](https://www.scienceeurope.org/about-us/members/?type=Research%20Funding%20Organisation%20(RFO))

Apart from the nationally administered funds mentioned before, that are still linked to the European Union, several European countries have their own national research programs that have a substantial budget for research financing. Going through the list of individual countries is time-consuming; nevertheless, all of the research funding organizations have an international character, therefore they should (in principle) be in line with EOSC's objectives and vision.

Support can be both "in cash" for the development, upgrade etc of services as well as "in kind," which would expand the range of possible contributions from different member states if they could pledge computing, data storage, support staff, or any other sort of assistance to EOSC.

7. Business Perspectives Assessment of NEANIAS Internal and External Cases

The objective of task 9.5: Innovation onboarding - Business cases analysis is to provide support to the business cases, selected in the frame of the NEANIAS Open Calls. The innovation onboarding of NEANIAS deals with analysing the business opportunities and providing support for these innovation cases. The task is led by innomine, and builds on the contribution of project partners Eunice, Incites, Ricoh, Cite and Ubiwhere. The analysis of the business cases aims at identifying their viability and potentially new business and collaboration opportunities associated with these business cases. In addition, this task, as part of the collaboration with NEANIAS aims at providing coaching to these business cases in terms of identifying innovation and business opportunities and support their evaluation by building on the sustainable perspectives.

Nine business cases are part of the NEANIAS project. Two of them are internal business cases, integrating the services of NEANIAS into their technology. These business cases are developed by two SMEs, Ubiwhere Lda (Portugal), and the Eunice Energy Group (Greece) that are part of the NEANIAS consortium. There are three business cases that are the winners of the first Open Call of NEANIAS, developed by the SMEs, Enaliatec (Greece), OWL (Portugal) and Geoinsight (Hungary). Their technical onboarding is in process, with the aim of integrating the services of NEANIAS. In addition, there are four winners selected in the frame of the second Open Call, namely DDQ BV (The Netherlands), Relief Applications (Spain), Sotiria Technology (Greece), and Walldone (Greece). This chapter contains detailed description about the winners of the first open call that their technical onboarding is in progress.

In the following sections these business cases are briefly presented focusing on their business perspectives.

7.1. Internal business cases

7.1.1. The B1 - Energy business innovation case - The Aegean Case1

The Aegean Case1 builds on and integrates the work of the AEGEAN Project, a 582MW wind energy project. The case acts as an “end-user” actor, utilizing and integrating elements provided by the NEANIAS services. Towards this direction, the atmospheric and underwater service elements are exploited and integrated into the business case, more specifically information associated with the seismic activity is utilised for the optimal design of the foundations of the wind turbines and other structures. Information related to the composition of the sea bottom (geological and bathymetric data) is applied in the designing of the route of the submarine cable. Furthermore, data referring to the atmosphere with an emphasis on wind profile as well as elements of extreme phenomena are exploited for the operation of the wind turbines. By using the services and data provided by NEANIAS, the AEGEAN project establishes a mechanism for locating and processing data, visualizing and delivering them. Both thematic and core NEANIAS services are tried out and will be integrated into the Eunice Energy Group led business case, aiming to design novel and innovative solutions. The goal of the AEGEAN project is to create interconnection of 23 uninhabited islets of the Aegean Sea with mainland Greece. The business case utilises the following services: U1- Bathymetry

mapping from acoustic data, U3 – Seabed classification from multispectral, multibeam data, and C4 Visual Discovery Framework in 2D and 3D tiling and maps.

7.1.1.1. The current status

The current status of the technical development is the following: the QGIS Plugin is fully functional and operational within the QGIS environment. The installation is available for end-users in a zip file format through the NEANIAS Gitlab page. The plugin is operational using data provided as input from the end-user. There are five types of input data: Bathymetry Raster, Seagrass Vector, Seabed Classification Raster, Cable Route Vector, Archaeological Sites Vector. The plugin documentation is included within NEANIAS documentation site, while the source code is included within NEANIAS Gitlab. The plugin is developed as a processing plugin for the QGIS software utilising its processing framework. It has the ability to operate the QGIS in four different working modes according to the user's research study needs, requirements and outputs. These are the following:

- Part1: Working with restricted areas (seagrass and archeological areas)
- Part2: Working with bathymetry (slope, terrain ruggedness, hillshades)
- Part3: Working with seabed classification
- Part4: Working with DC submarine link (cable route, slope)

There are filters available and different styles to narrow down the research and provide useful insights. The outputs of the QGIS Plugin include: Seagrass and restricted areas vectors and raster, Slope and hillshade raster layer (including histogram and interactive plot), classified bathymetry raster layer, bathymetry and seabed classification interactive plots, points along line vector layer. Until the end of the NEANIAS project, minor improvements are expected on the workflow of the Plugin. U1 and U3 services will be monitored through their final release phase for further enhancement of the relative integrated features of the plugin. There is a possible addition of further layers or processing steps providing more information on the DC cable's design to the users (e.g. shipwrecks locations).

An appropriate assessment and exploitation scheme, and the creation of the optimal commercialisation model of the plugin is in process in the frame of WP5 and WP9.

7.1.1.2. Impact and Value Proposition

The impact and value proposition of the business case are as follows:

Direct:

- Enhancement of end-user's project design accuracy through utilisation of provided data services (e.g. coastal dynamics) in combination to a wealth of data
- Supporting the development of projects similar to the AIGAI0 through integrations of the QGIS tool in end-user's daily business operations
- Global knowledge-strength sharing - owing to the QGIS tool's adaptiveness to all geographical and morphological input data
- Risk minimization and security increase related to the cable's installation
- Faster and effortless licensing issuance specifically during the required Environmental Impact Assessment by respective authorities

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Indirect:

- Supporting improvement in safety and reliability of the electricity supply to Crete and other Aegean islands through the Wind Farm interconnection by submarine links
- Contribution to the design and planning of the interconnection with Crete and thus, further aiding power transmission with Cyprus and Asia through the EuroAsia Interconnector
- Providing further interconnection options for other RES projects and extension of the designed wind park and its capacity through the provided data of the Thematic Services

7.1.1.3. Results in efficiency

Technical-wise:

- Quicker solutions when obstacles arise during project's development hindering the final outcome of an underwater cable installation project (e.g. archeological findings and military radar systems that are inside the cable installation area)
- Quicker and easier design processes of wind farm's electric interconnection based on the service's results, thus increasing efficiency within business operation
- Investigations, surveys and issuance of preliminary positive approvals by respective authorities prior to the implementations of the Production License procedure surely positively affects overall efficiency

Economic-wise:

- More accurate estimation of the required material and cost as the total length of cable is estimated as the tool identifies the optimal and allowed installation sites
- Cost and time savings related to labour costs required for execution of licensing and permission tasks

Licensing and Permission-wise:

- Increase of the security of installed submarine cable
- Increase of the efficiency and effectiveness of all necessary permission and licensing related procedures owing to completeness of the cable route study

7.1.1.4. Added values of NEANIAS

Adding to the services these above-mentioned features, leading to the development of the infrastructure. Cost-wise it can surely eliminate raw material.

External experts' validation: academia, research institutes, studies related to underwater cable installations. They expect to receive feedback from these sectors. They would like to see how this plugin could turn into a valuable asset for the energy community.

7.1.2. B2 - Environmental monitoring for smart cities case – The Smart City Case

The Smart City Case leverages NEANIAS services in the frame of a Smart City solution developed by NEANIAS Partner, UBIWHERE. UBIWHERE, a Portuguese company is focusing on creating an urban ecosystem network capable of monitoring, controlling, and forecasting not only the city's air quality performance, but also the city's dynamics using different sources of data (such as the traffic flow, energy consumption, geolocated touristic events, and even enabling multimodal trip planning). Such an integrated approach allows the testing of the business aspects of the services provided by NEANIAS. The services are used on the company's solution to ensure added innovative value. Both thematic and core NEANIAS services are analyzed and integrated into this business case, to deliver a high-quality service offering.

The urban platform that is developed provides real-time status of a region, collect information from several sources, and provides a general overview of short-term historical data. The platform can be used to support the capability of making decisions in real-time. The platform has the capability to calculate KPIs and sustainability indicators, to help cities track their progress towards the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and benchmark with sustainable cities and communities' indicators from ISO 37120/37122. The available indicators are associated with economy, society, energy, etc. In NEANIAS the focus is on the environmental part and more specifically the atmospheric domain.

The A3 Air quality estimation, monitoring and forecasting service implementation service is used enabling the forecasting of atmospheric conditions for urban planning. The AdamAPI, collects air and land surface temperature, precipitation (rain and snow), NO₂ concentration and vegetation assessment. The atmospheric service has been integrated, therefore the cities and decisionmakers can use this service aiming to assess greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from urban mobility sources. The service provides maps with hotspot and KPIs, recommending nature-based solutions to absorb CO₂.

Promotional activities

To get feedback for the platform, they are engaging end-users by participating in international events and workshops. In 2021, they participated in the following events: Smart City Expo World Congress – Barcelona, Portugal Smart Cities Summit – Lisbon, Air Quality workshop – Aveiro, Smart Cities Challenges panel – Braga, Portuguese Municipalities Association Congress – Aveiro. While in 2022 in the Open Event: Raise your voice towards sustainability – Aveiro. During the workshops with the University of Aveiro, that had around 30 participants, students were challenged to create innovative ideas towards sustainability, to test Ubiwhere Innovative Solutions and give their feedback on the developments made within the NEANIAS project.

The next steps include the continuation of the integration of ATMO-4CAST service, the validation of the administration interface of the platform, and the integration of the User Interface. The second release is expected at the end of June 2022.

The urban platform is validated with real data and is also deployed in Helsinki.

The main customers are expected to be public authorities that trust results coming out of research activities performed by academics. NEANIAS helps towards that direction as they can demonstrate that the solution is based in collaboration with academic partners.

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To support the further deployment of the platform UBIWHERE plans to participate in events and leverage EU funded projects.

Benefits from NEANIAS

The collaboration with NEANIAS have resulted the following outcomes:

- the enhanced correlation of in-situ monitoring stations in smart cities with satellite data for broader coverage
- the platform can analyze the loss of energy by creating a correlation of atmospheric conditions with green spaces
- ensure the reliability of operation and create a reliable forecasting service for environmental data
- create novel complementary features and broader coverage of data
- increase the efficiency of providing forecasting services in terms of weather and atmospheric conditions for smart city customers on planning scenarios and evaluate impact.

7.2. 1st wave of Open Call winners

7.2.1. EnaliaTec case

EnaliaTec is a spin-off company founded by CERTH-ITI in 2020 and aims to be involved in the research and development of underwater technologies by providing integrated software and hardware solutions to the marine scientific community. The experienced and specialised team aims to penetrate the market of underwater technology solutions by fulfilling the needs of the global diving research and professional community. The development and provisioning of solutions and services will be based on the know-how of the Laboratory of Virtual and Augmented Reality Laboratory of CERTH-ITI. In addition, EnaliaTec will be an exclusive commercial representative of the Italy-based company 3D Research S.R.L. offering some of its products and services. EnaliaTec team is working on the problem that oceans have very high density of marine litter on the sea floor. Thus, autonomous solutions that can operate at depths and conditions that divers cannot are needed. In addition, if the data are collected in less time the associated costs can be reduced. The automated identification of hotspots are required to organise more effective and efficiently underwater related missions. Blue Technologies impact the way a scientific diver works, bringing new methodologies and operations in various fields. The development of such solutions opened new opportunities for scientific diving, providing efficient underwater missions, safer diving conditions and effective underwater mapping.

The increase of population and related human activities in coastal areas create threats to the environment and to biodiversity. The technological advancements and developments made the aquatic world more accessible and safer for explorers using high tech revolutionary and innovative underwater system tools for the enhancement of their deep-water research. The availability of marine technologies and applications can assist professionals and the scientists conducting their underwater work more effectively.

EnaliaTec operates in the research and development of underwater technological solutions to meet the needs of global diving research and professional community. Its product portfolio

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includes DIVY, DEVSS, and Rodon100, together with services such as 3D illustration, 3D reconstruction of objects, and raising awareness concerning underwater marine environment through maritime museums, exhibition centres. MVPs are undergoing, including improved system of real-time monitoring of underwater environments, equipped with risk alert sensors. Remotely operated vehicle (ROV) with haptic arms, georeferenced autonomous underwater vehicle (g-AUV) with embedded AI and ML technology capable of performing autonomous navigations.

The services provided by Enaliattec are:

- *3D profile of the sea bottom (3D seabed mapping) with DEVSS*: 3D maps can be generated using visual data provided by either multiple cameras (stereo systems) or single cameras (monocular systems). 3D mapping process can be aided by navigation data if available or can be carried out using image processing only, ensuring high accuracy for the resulting 3D models.
- *3D Reconstruction of underwater cultural heritage artefacts*: Non-invasive 3D reconstruction techniques, such as the photogrammetry and the 3D laser scanning, can be applied to underwater archaeological sites. This way, highly faithful digital copies of the fields and their specific objects can be obtained.
- *Immersive 3D Virtual Diving Content Creation and visualisation systems*: content creation and visualisation hardware of 3D archaeological finds, supporting Virtual Immersions or any other software.

Enaliattec offers the construction of high-quality signs and labels for underwater use in a variety of materials, sizes, thickness, and coatings based on the requirements of the application of use and the final user. Coatings consist of environmentally friendly and nontoxic materials with anti-fouling characteristics that disallow biological deposits on subsea structures. The engineering team can undertake the architectural design of custom-made underwater signage systems, including graphic design printing, dimensioning and material selection, based on site and use requirements. Upon request, the safe installation of a custom-made signage system on site is possible. All signs are offered together with their anchorage system, buoys, ropes, screws, and other supporting accessories. EnaliaTec delivered to the Region of Peloponnese a full underwater and on land signage system of the Pavlopetri archaeological site. The system included the construction of 18 underwater signs with special anti-fouling specifications, a set of colorful floating signage buoys, and an information sign on land. Pavlopetri prehistoric settlement site is accessible to swimmers from the sandy shore and now, with the signage system installed, the tour of the site is allowed with a mask and a snorkel. The visitor can easily identify vaulted tombs and cist graves, rooms, walls, streets, etc. inside the underwater site.

The innovative idea that EnaliaTec aims to implement and validate within 1st NEANIAS Open Call is “3D Seabed Mapping and Classification Utilizing Sonar-Based Information”. Knowledge of underwater (UW) seabed bathymetry and morphology has significantly influenced their understanding of planet’s dynamics. However, the detection and/or recognition of specific objects, landmarks, etc. in UW environments is not only a difficult task, but also it is time-consuming and expensive. The MVP development is undergoing, G-AUV aims to complete

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missions towards monitoring the marine environment, the detection and categorisation of objects, like marine litter, plastics, wrecks, amphoras, corrals, geological formations. This will be equipped with cameras lighting system, environmental sensors, bathometer and acoustic sensors from HW side and AI and ML algorithms from the SW side. The final product will be a low-cost georeferenced AUV, easy deployable by two people from a 7m pneumatic boat. The envisioned system will be comprised by two beacons, which will create a georeferenced environment up to 120 m of depth in an area of 400x 200 m.

Market potential:

The market growth is largely driven by the rising population levels, the ongoing installation of environmental stations, development of environment friendly industries, and rising awareness on pollution monitoring. Increased technological advancements about data collection sensors and technologies are anticipated to bolster the demand for survey equipment. Developments such as the use of laser sensors and satellite-based bathymetry, offer benefits in conducting bathymetric surveys. With the advancements in technology, the adoption and application of high-tech underwater solutions are increased across various industry sectors. The rising need for continuous surveillance of submerged ocean areas and the increasing demand for underwater robots have played significant role in growth of the global market.

Promotional activities:

The promotional tools to be utilised are direct sales with free trials, scientific specialised conferences (e.g. related to underwater technology), diving exhibitions and conferences, scientific publications, strategic partnerships with diving equipment companies, newsletters/brochures/diving magazines. EnaliaTec foresees opportunities for expansion by offering services with low cost in order to operate within a highly competitive environment.

Benefits from NEANIAS

They are interested in Underwater thematic area, while they are willing to use the UW-MAP “Seabed Classification from Multispectral Multibeam Data” and UW-BAT “Underwater Bathymetry Processing” services from the service catalogue. EnaliaTec through NEANIAS Open Call will have the opportunity to develop a novel system for categorizing objects and landmarks at 3D seabed. During the three-month Proof-of-Concept (PoC) implementation and evaluation, EnaliaTec will develop, test and evaluate a novel idea in real-life environments. The overall implementation will be accelerated by utilizing ready services (UW-BAT and UW-MAP NEANIAS services) solving difficult problems to UW science. Finally, potential joint exploitation of the system between EnaliaTec and NEANIAS corresponding partners (TELEDYNE and ATHENA) will be studied and evaluated.

7.2.2. Our Watch Leads - OWL, LDA

LDA is a start-up that is democratizing the access to Satellite Earth Observation data. This is achieved through the automatized processing of satellite data, filtered by predictive algorithms to inform the target sectors: Construction, Real Estate, Agriculture and Smart cities.

Similar to the medical diagnosis techniques they use an X-ray or an MRI exam. OWL’s Satellite Earth Observation products provide a better comprehension of our cities or rural territory

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achieving more effective solution that are based on the concrete data and mapping of the intervention sites.

The diagnostic tools created by OWL derive from Satellite Remote Sensing data processed in Python, assessing several square km simultaneous, with higher velocity and more levels of concrete data compared to in-situ traditional methods, such as topographic surveys. These advantages are more important considering the growing tendencies for remote work or in periods such as the current times, with COVID-19, when mobility is limited. As an example, one of OWL's products, the "Good2Build" plan, locates the areas with more biodiversity, land deformations and waterways, allowing to avoid the artificialization of these zones, which simultaneously protects the environment and saves money in the building's foundations' structure, waterproofing and in land containment.

Benefits from NEANIAS

Looking at the NEANIAS open call, OWL aims to create two products the "Good2Breathe" and the "Bad2Breathe" plans, where the Atmospheric Thematic Services can be used to map and rate urban areas and real estate properties, in terms of Air Quality Estimation, Monitoring and Forecasting, combined with the data that derive from OWL's Satellite Earth Observation products for vegetation location and health, promoting or demoting practices that, respectively, either provide good or bad urban comfort.

OWL intends to use Atmospheric Thematic Services, more specifically the Air Quality Estimation, Monitoring and Forecasting service. It is a scientific fact that vegetation can mitigate the effects of air pollution. Within that scope, OWL intends to quantify air pollution and understand its temporal evolution in the urban context, using the Air Quality Estimation, Monitoring and Forecasting service. This information will allow the mapping of critical/opportunity cities, which then will be cross-examined using 10m resolution Satellite data, to process indices such as the Land use classification, the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index, the Moisture Index and the Land Surface Temperature. Thus, it will be possible to correlate the urban green spaces' location and health, and the levels of air pollution, as well as to locate "Brownfields", that can be converted into urban green spaces. The added value expected from NEANIAS is the combination of valuable data to achieve better diagnostics and solution prescriptions, to promote and communicate these solutions, as well as to find more potential investors or customers.

7.2.3. GEOInsight

GEOInsight is a spin-off company founded by the research fellows of the Big Geospatial Research Lab at the Research Centre for Astronomy and Earth Sciences (hereinafter referred to as "CSFK"). Members of GEOInsight have been conducting applied research since 2017 in location data modelling, simulation and forecast. The software development team was formed during comprehensive human mobility research based on Magyar Telekom's unique mobile cellular data, covering domestic network traffic for two years. GEOInsight's work focuses mainly on human mobility modelling, applying primarily – but not exclusively – telecommunication big data (mobile cell, Bluetooth). They developed locational intelligence software products based on research findings and they are examining the commercialisation possibilities in two application fields:

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- Disaster management: real-time, spatially and temporally targeted location-based alarming systems serving public management purposes
- Location-based marketing and location intelligence: development of visitor management systems, targeted marketing and recommendation systems

In 2021, the GEOInsight research team began experimental development in mobile cell data-based prediction of human movement. Individual and mass motion trajectories along various parameters were simulated using graph analysis and in-depth learning methods. Based on this research, the predictive power of the mobility forecast model based on mobile cell data is comparable to that of navigation data.

Georadio application is the data generation module that is embedded in profiling and segmentation software. Georadio generates mass human mobility data while protecting privacy. Georadio applies the long-established Bluetooth technology in a disruptive way by creating point maps and strictly avoiding trajectory mapping to keep limits of confidentiality. The method is inspired by academic practice applied in human movement research. Georadio, embedded in the complex profiling and segmentation software, was presented at the Hungarian Future Trade meetup and at the Fintech Show during the Fall of 2021. The current stage of the Georadio refers to TRL 3 and has demonstrated the functionality in a small-scale test during the summer of 2021. The test verified the applicability and functionality that can be achieved by further development of the software. Additional modules that serve to strengthen Georadio selling point are in different readiness levels. The related profiling algorithms were already built into the query interface but not tested yet, so its readiness can be set to TRL 2.

Open science and open data are considered as values for GEOInsight. Their academic staff appreciates and encourages free access to research findings and data. European Research Infrastructures plays a crucial role in their work because Copernicus Earth Observation Programme enriches the mobility forecast model with valuable data. They borrow computation capacity from the high-scale ELKK Cloud Programme, part of the European Research Infrastructure network. GEOInsight undertakes a commitment in NEANIAS project to communicate the values of EOSC and transferred within the national and international professional network that GEOInsight actively participated in, such as the Hungarian Artificial Intelligence Coalition and Alliance for Enterprises in Informatics, Telecommunication and Energy in Hungary.

Georadio's business model is highly dependent on the ecosystem that will be applied. The go-to-market strategy is two-tiered. First, they will take advantage of their competitive lead in data generation technologies and locational data intelligence and elaborate the modular mass mobility sensing and profiling product. They target the digital marketing agencies and fintech sector with the first-generation product. After 18-24 months, when their technology gains momentum in the locational intelligence and business consultation market, they will shift the focus to high-scale urban data platforms, IoT services and software development. Internet of things will be soon enriched by the notion of the internet of people. Data platforms, such as digital twin programmes, need valuable data on human behaviour to successfully utilise the unprecedented technological results they possess. The reason behind the data hunger of urban data platforms is that the industries digitisation runs up technology development. The spreading of those technologies to the B2C implies a vast market to open up. However, the

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way to successful commercialisation of industrial technologies leads through better knowing individual behaviour, motivation, and goals. Human mobility has a solid correlation to lifestyle, which implies that locational data analytics and locational intelligence are crucial to open up the market for internet of people technologies.

GEOInsight has following competitive advantages:

- Georadio is a disruptive software solution that has never been used for mass human mobility detection before
- They are early developers in the location-based profiling market and have a time advantage in technology development,
- Data type-independent data processing platform that allows the implementation of the profiling procedure for various location data,
- Georadio and profiling and recommendation system as a modular software provides a complex solution to the business pain of the data shortage and the lack of profiling insights at the same time
- GEOInsight provides modular algorithms which can be applied both autonomously and complementary
- Georadio works both indoors and outdoors, apart from GNSS/GPS receivers that only operate outdoors.
- Experimental developments in advanced analytical procedures (mobility forecasting, simulation),
- Deep knowledge of global trends in the potential market, active relationships with domestic players,
- Scalable computing capacity,
- Extensive methodological preparation in the field of geolocation data management, analysis and visualisation,
- Curiosity and ability to capture complex patterns: knowledge of topological relations, propagation phenomena, patterns and regularities of exploratory and rule-following mobility behaviour.

Georadio uses Bluetooth-based geolocation, which is energy-saving against the widely used GPS tracking systems. Mobile devices do not tolerate locational data retrieval for a longer period, making GPS-based tracking less capable for mass data mining technologically, financially, and from a data protection point of view. Raw data acquired from location data aggregators (Datarade, Narrative, Gravy Analytics) provide no context and behavioural insights, and there are issues in representativity and volume of data. The only working solution they could identify for locational data mining, similar to our technology, is Coinapp.

Due to the effect of COVID, Geoinsight's business case's onboarding could be started with delay, together with the onboarding of the 2nd Open Call winners.

8. Conclusions – Future Steps

Although NEANIAS services have just been onboarded, there are several issues that should be initially understood and addressed for their commercialisation and sustainability.

In this deliverable, the services under investigation were initially described. Services following the free business model (with no revenues) were examined. The cost elements required to run these services have been identified.

Meetings with the providers of NEANIAS services were then carried out in order to discuss the selected elements as well as the potential model for the assessment of services sustainability. The discussion revealed that the service providers were not aware of the elements and all the costs related to their services. Thus, it was decided to simplify both the model to be used and the required inputs. Spreadsheets asking for data related to existing and future funding, resources dimensioning rules and prices, implementation costs and other costs have been created and distributed to the service providers. Several meetings have been carried out in order to better explain to service providers the required inputs and reach an acceptable level of the provided data/info.

The provided data were used in the technoeconomic model in order to derive the appropriate results. The results showed that all the services are not self-sustained and need funding in order to ensure their sustainability. This was somehow expected since the services under investigation have no revenues. The required funding for services' sustainability was estimated. Potential sources of funding were provided and described. In some cases (services), service providers have already secured part of the required funding by either other EU projects or by National programs.

Finally, the business perspectives of both NEANIAS internal and external cases have been investigated. A description of all cases was initially provided. The business model of each case including customers, revenue streams and costs was presented and discussed.

The scope of the deliverable is to provide an insight of NEANIAS free services sustainability. These can also be used as guidance to NEANIAS partners and other members of EoSC ecosystem interested in participating in the development and provision of similar services.

As a next step, D9.6 will present the final outcomes for the sustainability of NEANIAS services including "commercial" services that is services expecting revenues.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
ADN	Astra Data Navigator
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AUV	Autonomous Underwater Vehicle
CAESAR	Compact and Extended Sources Automated Recognition
CEF	Connecting European Facility
CF	Cohesion Fund
DCF	Discounted Cash Flow
EAFRD	European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development
EC	European Commission
EFSI	European Fund for Strategic Investments
EIB	European Investment Bank
EIT	European Institute of Innovation and Technology
EMFF	European Maritime and Fisheries Fund
EO	Earth Observation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ESA	European Space Agency
ESF	European Social Fund
ESI	European Structural and Investment
EU	European Union
GB	Giga Bytes
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IRR	Internal Rate of Return
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
MS	Member States
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NPC	National Project Coordinator
NPV	Net Present Value
OWL	Our Watch Leads
PoC	Proof-of-Concept
PPP	Public Private Partnership
PV	Present Value
ROV	Remotely Operated Vehicle
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UW	Underwater
VLKB	ViaLactea Knowledge Base
VLVA	ViaLactea Visual Analytic